

World Gifted

NEWSLETTER OF THE WORLD COUNCIL FOR GIFTED AND TALENTED CHILDREN

VOL. 4, No. 1

MARCH 1983

Manila Seminars to Feature World-Wide Coverage

Representatives from all parts of the globe will offer seminars at the Fifth World Conference on the Gifted and Talented to be held in Manila, August 2-6, 1983. The Conference will aim at exploring problems, issues and practices in identification, recognition, and development of the gifted and talented in both developed and developing countries.

In addition to keynote speakers announced previously (Jean Houston, Eleazar Shmueli, James Gallagher, Harry Passow, and Paul Torrance), a number of experts have submitted their papers for presentation. They include Klaus Weinschenk and Klaus Urban from Germany, M. H. Novaes Mira (Brazil), Beale Hermelin (UK), Jean-Claude Grubar (France), Nouri Jaf-far (Iraq), J. S. Neethling (South Africa), Lorraine Wilgosh, Robert Mulcahy and Eugene Lehman (Canada), and Janet Riesen, Ann Bachtel-Nash and Norman Mirman (USA) among others. The Deputy Minister of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Philippines, Dean Lucracia Kasilag of the National Arts Center, and other Philippine educators will present papers on topics related to Gifted Education policies and the economics of manpower development. The deadline for submission of papers has been extended, and a form for proposals is included in this newsletter.

Some invitations for travel and cultural events have been extended to participants. Delegates have been invited to visit the National Arts Center of the Philippines, a school for gifted students at the secondary level. The Conference will include the formal opening reception at the Fiesta Pavilion of the Manila Hotel which will be sponsored by the Ministry of Education and Culture and will be open to all participants.

A number of local tours to places such as Pagsanjan Falls, the famous waterfall that cascades from cliffs into a deep pool, Tagaytay City with its unusual lake formed by vast volcanic eruption, and Baguio, the summer capital of the Philippines, have been

AIR-FARE DISCOUNTS TO MANILA

Philippine Airlines, the official airline of the Manila Gifted Conference, is offering attractive fares to Conference participants. A 40 percent discount is available off first class, business, and economy fares, all of which are free of restrictions. The super-saver fare is not subject to discount, but the reduced economy fare is lower than supersaver and does not carry the supersaver restrictions.

In order to secure the 40 percent discount, participants must identify themselves as attending the Manila Gifted Conference and must make reservations directly through PAL and not through a travel agent. Sample airfares as of January, 1983, from the United States are listed below. Because of currency fluctuations, PAL could not quote rates from other parts of the world. In general, rates from Europe are somewhat higher, from Australia somewhat lower. Some increases in fares worldwide are anticipated this Spring.

PAL ONE-WAY FARES TO MANILA AS OF JANUARY 1983

	Regular Economy	With 40 percent discount
Chicago	\$945	\$567
Dallas	884	531
New York	1007	605
Los Angeles, San Francisco, Seattle	716	430

Some travel agencies (e.g. University Flights, 420 Riverside Drive, New York, NY 10025) are offering discounts off Supersaver rates. If using such services, please ask them to identify you with Manila Gifted Conference when booking on PAL so that World Council may be credited with the booking.

arranged by conference organizers. Dr. Wutien Wu of the National Taiwan Normal University in the Republic of China, has invited participants to visit Taiwan before or after the Conference.

Please write to me for further information.

--Aurora Roldan

PRESIDENT'S CORNER

In times of great transition in society it is easy to grasp the special importance of educating those minds that have the greatest capabilities for creativity, productive thinking and leadership. While many nations in the world are still struggling to become industrial, some industrial nations seem intent on proceeding into a post-industrial "information" society. The emphasis will be on the production of ideas and communication rather than the production of goods.

The evolution of the computer has made this possible offering us a chance to extend our intellect, even as a telescope extends human vision. Those gifted children and youth among us will play an inevitably important role in both transitions--towards industrialization or beyond it.

How important then are those who prepare these gifted individuals for their productive work? A flood of biographies and autobiographies has confirmed the important role of teacher and mentor in the development of productive adults. Rarely has such a role been more important; rarely has it been less appreciated. One purpose of the World Council is to remind people of the importance of education to that intellectual and personal development and also how important that special attention be paid to the type and form of education they receive.

--James J. Gallagher

GIFTED INTERNATIONAL: NEW ISSUES

Vol. 1, No. 2, of *Gifted International*, was placed in the mail in mid-January to members of the World Council. The issue features articles by D.T.E. Marjoram (UK) on "Creativity and the Gifted Child," Vaune and George Ainsworth-Land (US) on "Learning and Creating," Tudor Rickards and Jenny Sykes (UK) on "Classroom of the Future," John Jones (New Zealand) on "Gifted at University," Mary Meeker (US) on "Teaching of Intelligence," Nahid Dehlavi (Iran) on "Development of Children's Conceptions," Marvin J. Gold (US) on "A Personal View of Developments in Israel," Mario J. Gamba on "Pilot Institute in Chile," Jon Wiles and Joseph Bondi (US) on "Creative Thinking," J. Bina Machado and M. H. Novaes Mira (Brazil) on "Perspectives in Brazil," James W. Ott (US) "Optimizing Human Resources in a Multi-National Corporation," Abdalia M. Soliman (Kuwait) "Developing Gifted Children in Relation to Their Needs and the Needs of Their Countries," and Frieda Painter (UK) on "Research on Gifted Children in Hertfordshire."

The first issue of Volume 2 is in final stages of editing and will appear in the late Spring. It focuses on curriculum for the gifted in a variety of countries, including New Zealand, Canada, Bulgaria, West Germany, Israel, United States, South Africa, Taiwan, Australia and the Philippines.

The authors represented in these articles are Harry Wagschal (Canada), D. W. Freeman (New Zealand), Verna Tribe (Canada), R. W. Callow (UK), Dorothy and Forest Armstrong (US), Nan Dean, Joan Sigler and Veronica Church (Canada), Rachel Zorman and Aryeh Lubling (Israel), Wei-Fan Kuo (Taiwan), Susan Allan (US), and J. Ca-wood (South Africa).

The journal is included in the membership fee for World Council members. Other persons may order issues at \$7 each or \$12 for the year from Trillium Press, P.O. Box 921, New York, NY 10159.

Exec. Sec'y's Gifted Text Reissued

The Leadership Training Institute has republished *Education of the Gifted/Talented* by Milton J. Gold with an extensive Epilogue to fill in developments in gifted education since its original appearance. Order from Ventura Co. Supt. of Schools, LTI Publications 535 E. Main St., Ventura, CA 93009 (\$18.95).

Newsletter of the
WORLD COUNCIL FOR GIFTED & TALENTED CHILDREN

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HELP WANTED: A REQUEST FOR PROPOSALS

Milton Gold has informed the Executive Committee of his intention to withdraw as Executive Secretary as of September 1, 1983. Proposals are invited for change in the administration of the Secretariat, including both location and personnel. Information on structure and finances of the office are available from the Executive Secretary. The following procedures have been established for submitting proposals, with a deadline of April 1, 1983:

1. Interested agencies should inform the Executive Secretary who will respond with information indicated above.
2. The Executive Committee will receive proposals, rank them, and make a tentative recommendation in April if possible to members of the Delegate Assembly who will be asked to respond by a reasonable date.

The following criteria will be used in reviewing proposals and are suggested as a format:

1. The proposal must take into account the limited financial resources of the World Council and should indicate institutional support that will be available for professional personnel, administrative services, space, and office equipment.
2. The proposing agency should have a recognized center or program in education/research on the gifted.
3. Proposals must come from an institution and not from an individual.
4. Previous experience and activity in the World Council will be considered.
5. The offer should be for a period of four years and be renewable.
6. Names and vitae of key persons should be included in the proposal.

THINKING ABILITIES TOURNAMENT

"High level thinking" competitions have gone world-wide with announcement of "The World's First Thinking Olympiad," to be conducted at the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji, July 5-9, 1983. The first tournament was actually held in 1980, and succeeding competitions have included distinguished lecturers including "Marco" Meirovitz, the inventor of Master Mind. The purpose is to raise the thinking skills of participants.

Fourteen areas are included, among them chess, math, reasoning, geography, history, science, current events, and a "talent quest."

Write: Secretary, Fiji International Thinking Abilities Tournament, P. O. Box 2071, Suva, Fiji, South Pacific.

CALL FOR PAPERS

The response to the call for papers to be given at the Manila Conference has been gratifying from the Far East but has been slow in coming from points more remote from the Philippines. To encourage a greater flow from these countries, the Organizing Committee has extended the deadline for submission of proposals to the end of February. Later papers may be accepted but they may be too late for printing in the Conference Program.

The Committee hopes that prospective participants are not hiding their light under a bushel. Their hope, of course, is that the Conference will be truly international in its representation of research and development activities from all over the world.

Persons who have not yet submitted a proposal are urged to do so. A form is included on page 4 of this newsletter.

YEARBOOK; OTHER COUNCIL PUBLICATIONS

The first *Yearbook* of the World Council will appear late this Spring, consisting of selected papers of the Fourth World Conference on the Gifted and Talented held in Montreal in 1981. The *Yearbook* is being initiated as a biennial in the expectation that it will become an annual publication in the future. The 1983 *Yearbook* is being edited by a committee under Bruce Shore in Canada. Persons who attended the 1981 Conference will receive copies as part of their registration fee. The price will be announced later for other persons desiring copies. Major addresses at the Conference will be included with other papers chosen from almost 300 that were presented.

Gifted Children: Reaching Their Potential, edited by James J. Gallagher, is the Proceedings of the San Francisco Conference, 1977; a limited number of copies are still available. Order from Trillium Press, P.O. Box 921, New York, NY 10159, at \$15.50 US. Proceedings of the 1979 Conference in Jerusalem, *Gifted Children: Challenging Their Potential*, were edited by Alan Kramer. That volume, too, may be ordered from Trillium Press at the same price.

Persons desiring to have a complete set of these significant Conference Proceedings may order copies of *Looking to Their Future*, papers from the First Conference, held in London in 1975, which have been reprinted. Send a Sterling draft for £5 drawn on a UK bank to NAGC, 1 So. Audley St., London W1Y 5DQ, England.

Back issues of *GATE* may also be ordered from Trillium Press at \$6.

GIFTED AND TALENTED CHILDREN, YOUTH AND ADULTS
THEIR SOCIAL PERSPECTIVES AND CULTURE

Fifth World Conference on Gifted and Talented Children
Manila, Philippines, August 2-6, 1983

Call For Papers – Proposal and Abstract Form

Deadline has been extended; however, papers submitted after February 28 may be too late to be announced in the program.

Mail this form to:
Manila Gifted Conference
P. O. Box 639
Greenhills 3113
Metro Manila
Philippines

Please Print or Type:

Presenter's name: _____

Institution : _____

Mailing Address: _____

Title or Topic of Proposal: _____

Type of Session:

Lecture Forum: _____

Round Table Discussion: _____

Poster Session: _____ Audio-Visual Equipment Needed: _____

Co-Author: _____

Institution: _____ Country: _____

Abstract: (Clearly state content and relation to the theme of the conference. Please limit abstract to space provided.)

I acknowledge the prerogative of the Program Committee to translate this abstract or to make minor revisions for editorial consistency if it is accepted for presentation at the Fifth World Conference on Gifted and Talented Children. I also affirm that the presentation is specially prepared for this Conference and has not been published or proposed elsewhere for presentation in its present form or in substantial part.

Signature

Date

GLEANINGS FROM TRIENNIAL CHILDREN'S BANNER OF PEACE ASSEMBLY

By Joyce Luhrs

I returned from the Triennial Children's Banner of Peace Assembly in Sofia, Bulgaria at the end of August. It was very exciting! Some of the most gifted children in the arts from over 100 countries were there. I learned about the new educational system in Bulgaria, and I had a chance to meet some of the teachers from the science/math school in Sofia. Similar schools exist elsewhere in Bulgaria but not to the same extent as in the Soviet Union. I am continuing my research on the educational systems in Cuba and the Soviet Union. I had a chance to meet delegates from these countries while in Bulgaria. The Cubans had chosen the best young dancers and singers in the country. I would imagine that they came from special schools. I know Alicia Alonso, the ballerina, recruits young children at the age of seven to attend her school; so I suspect the same is done for other areas in the arts. Unfortunately, there was not enough time to find out about specific programs and schools for the gifted in these countries today.

I have enough information to put together a comprehensive sociological treatise on the educational systems in these countries. The drawback, of course, is that as far as I can tell no one in the U.S. is doing any research about the gifted in Cuba. Articles have been written about the literacy campaign and mention has been made about special science/math schools in Cuba, but nothing in any great detail about the gifted and talented.

I learned about the School of Exact Sciences in Cuba which opened in 1980. What little has been written about such schools by Americans is often biased. Marvin Leiner wrote about the school and took the attitude that such schools build elitism and go against the Socialist doctrine of equality. This is true to some extent, but for Cuba the benefits of advancement in technology based upon educating the brightest youths is neglected by many educators in the U.S. Journalists such as Fred Ward and free-lance writers such as Jonathan Kozol have been a little bit more open-minded in their writings about special science/math schools. At the times of their publications, Cuba leaned toward polytechnical schools such as the Lenin Vocational School to take in and teach the brightest scientific minds in Cuba but of a vocational-production aspect which is now being neglected in special science/math schools. Information is lacking

about what special schools exist for the talented in science/math in Cuba, tests used for assessment to enter, student and teacher selection, facilities, backgrounds of students, popular attitudes toward such schools and in general towards special instruction for the gifted and talented, vocational orientation (if any), and foremost comparisons of the Cuban system to other socialist/communist countries.

I should appreciate it if persons having information about special schools and programs for the gifted and talented in Cuba or the Soviet Union in science and math would write to me, Box 1171, Oberlin College, Oberlin, OH 44074.

MANILA: A GATEWAY TO WESTERN PACIFIC

The 1983 World Conference in Manila is the first international meeting on the gifted to be held in the Far East and the first to be conducted in a developing country. It offers special opportunities for study of the Philippine culture and for visits to a number of countries, each with a unique history and traditions.

Filipinos call their home the Pearl of the Pacific, "a seven thousand island paradise of tropical flora and fauna, virgin lands and waters. Here, Spanish galleons, Chinese junks and Malayan balangayas merged their riches to endow a people with the gentleness of the East and the open smile of the West. At the heart lies the city of Manila, a cosmopolitan city of juxtaposed contrasts. Several languages are spoken in these 7000 islands, but English serves as a lingua franca within the diversity of native tongues.

Headquarters for the Conference will be in two magnificent hotels which are offering specially low prices to participants. Tropical fruits are available in abundance as is seafood which boggles the mind of visitors from the West. Embroidered articles, dresses and blouses for men and women are a specialty, and prices are right!

Manila is also a jumping-off place for romantic names in the East: Hong Kong, Kuala Lumpur, Jakarta, Bangkok, Taipei, Tokyo, Singapore, Shanghai, Nanking, Beijing, and "down under" to New Zealand and Australia. Tours to a number of these places are being organized by a Conference Committee. Discounts will be offered if a sufficient number of people apply for particular tours.

Further information may be secured by writing to the Manila Gifted Secretariat, P.O. Box 639, Greenhills 3113, Metro Manila, Philippines, or the World Council office in New York.

In This Issue-- BOOKS IN REVIEW --Mind over Matter

Lewis, D., & Greene, J. *Thinking Better*. New York: Wade Publishers, 1982, \$10.95.

Authors Lewis and Greene, of the Mind Potential Study Group in London, share six years of research on peak mental performance. The five-step method is designed to increase every major aspect of intellectual performance. A pre-post test is included with the study methods said to boost IQ scores by 50 percent. Even casual readers will find the book full of mnemonic aids and insights into intellectual test item construction.

Papert, S. *Mindstorms*. New York: Harper Colophon Books, 1980, \$6.95.

A combination of children, computers and ideas led MIT Professor Papert to chronicle the development of LOGO, the computer language in which even young children can program. He is convinced that what and how an individual learns is dependent upon the models available. The book extends from genetic epistemology and Piaget's cognitive emphasis to inclusion of concern for affect.

Gould, S.J. *The Mismeasure of Man*. New York: W. W. Norton, 1981, \$14.95.

Harvard Professor Gould itemizes damage done by testers down through history in the name of biological determinism and challenges factor analysis. A concluding chapter refutes the approach of Arthur Jensen and the human sociobiologists. Gould leaves the message that debunking is a positive science and the conviction that humans are learning animals.

Jensen, A.R. *Straight Talk about Mental Tests*. New York: Macmillan, 1981, \$12.95.

In a comprehensive but non-technical vein, psychologist Jensen (U. of California) defines the "general" factor of intelligence and explains test construction, administration and evaluation. His position on the controversial topic of black-white IQ gap is clearly stated.

Butler-Adam, J. *Language Ability in Children of High Measured Intelligence*. Durban (Private Bag X54001, Natal, So. Africa): University of Durban-Westville.

Relationships between language and thought are explored using actual children's dialogues to assist teachers responsible for teaching able youngsters with skill and understanding. The importance of sensitive, skilled teaching is underscored in Butler-Adams' findings.

CORRECTION: Our last issue incorrectly spelled Nancy Polette's name with an "F". Nancy, your book, 3R's for the Gifted, rates an "A" with

us and so do you for catching the "typo".

NEW UNITS FOR TEACHERS

Gallagher, J.J. *et al. Leadership Unit: The Use of Teacher-Scholar Teams to Develop Units for the Gifted*. NY: Trillium Press, 1982, \$12.50.

This team effort has produced a practical unit for the middle school years and documents the method by which such units can be cooperatively created. The evaluation of the project contains valuable insights into the plan.

Freeman, D. *A New Way to Use Your Brain*. NY: Trillium Press, 1982, \$10.

Freeman's innovative "cookbook" of 30 lessons for home or school develops thinking skills in early childhood years deliciously. Sample responses of children show logic, creativity, problem solving and critical thinking actively involved in food experiences.

McGreevy, A. *My Book of Things and Stuff*. Mansfield Center, CT: Creative Learning Press, 1982, \$8.95.

A felicitous blend of theory-based practice, reproducible examples, and current references fills this interest questionnaire adapted especially for young children by a teacher working with gifted students.

Heuer, J., *et al. M.A.G.I.C. K.I.T.S.: Meaningful Activities for the Gifted*. Mansfield, CT: Creative Learning Press, 1982, \$8.95.

Portable interest center ideas for implementing Renzulli's Type I and II Enrichment in 21 topics are presented here on perforated sheets.

* * *

Maker, C.J. *Teaching Models in Education of the Gifted*. Rockville, MD: Aspen Systems, 1982, \$30.50.

A comprehensive text which reviews most appropriate curriculum models, Maker's work provides examples from Bloom, Krathwohl, Bruner, Guilford, Kohlberg, Parnes, Renzulli, Taba, Taylor, Treffinger, and Williams. Each model is examined for research on effectiveness with nongifted and gifted students. Use of an eclectic approach which accommodates local conditions is outlined in the final chapter.

Skolnick, J., *et al. How to Encourage Girls in Math & Science*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1982, \$7.95.

Parents and educators alike will find this an important collection of issues and answers, activities and techniques addressing the sex role socialization effects on skills and on confidence among girls. An outstanding work with practical applications.

--Beverly Goodloe-Kaplan

GIFTED NEWS WORLD - W I D E

REPORT FROM ITALY

Menotti Cossu, editor of the *Mensa Italia Bulletin*, has sent us a copy which includes his article on "the gifted child problem. The article synthetically shows how this problem is dealt with by the world countries, takes into consideration what has been done in Italy until now and gives a quantitative evaluation of the gifted children who would need special help in Italy." Having interested a politician, Dr. Cossu succeeded in getting a grant from the Sicilian Region to pay a large part of the debts of The Gifted Children's Hamlet which opened in Sicily in 1967 and closed eight years later for lack of funds. "The founder, Don Calogera La Placa, is now hoping to begin again the activity of his hamlet."

Nevertheless, Dr. Cossu declares, things have not changed in Italy. There, too, education is tarred with the brush of elitism. Dr. Cossu is working with *Mensa Italia* "to put the problem in the proper light here in Italy, so that it is lived less emotionally, is more serenely evaluated and more seriously studied."

GIFTS FROM BRITISH COLUMBIA

Periodically we are favored with a compendious journal (this time 295 pages) from the Association of Educators of Gifted, Talented, and Creative Children in British Columbia (Canada), published by the B.C. Teachers' Federation. President of the Association is Linda Lewis, a member of the World Council Assembly of Delegates. The Fall 1982 issue, by way of example, includes announcements, chapter reports, children's writings, conference reports (this one on microcomputers), "thinking activities," teaching units which make up the bulk of the publication, sources of information for parents as well as teachers, and an article by John Gowan for parents of gifted children. Address: 105-2235 Burrard St., Vancouver, B.C., Canada V6J 3H9.

NATIONAL MEETING IN AUSTRALIA

The Australian Commonwealth Schools Commission has called a National Conference on the Education of Gifted and Talented Children "as part of its concern for all children" to be held at Melbourne University August 28-31, 1983. Focusing on needs, programs and research in this area, the Conference "will cover programmes for pre-school, primary and secondary students, for teacher education, both initial and inservice, as well as the concerns of par-

ents and the community." For information, write E. B. Start, Dept. of Education, University of Melbourne, Vic., 3052.

NATIONAL G/T ORGANIZATION FOR SOUTH AFRICA

Jock Omond reports an effort to establish a national forum for education of the gifted in South Africa. He has invited secretaries of the presently operating societies for the gifted, local and regional, to meet and discuss a proposal to establish a national council for the gifted and/or an "interest group" on gifted children within the South African Association for the Advancement of Education. The SAAAE has already chosen "Teaching the Gifted Child" as its 1983 Conference theme. Professor Omond hopes that this focus will help local groups in South Africa to coalesce in a national organization.

NEW ZEALAND NEWSLETTER

Gifted Children: Their Future--Our Challenge is the magazine of the New Zealand Association for Gifted Children. It offers an interesting melange of news on the gifted, opportunities for them, excerpts from articles on the gifted and items written by the children (*bless 'em*) themselves. The September 1982 issue features the report of the President, Anne J. Murrell, which is a good example of the activities of an advocacy organization. These include recruitment of members, publication of the magazine, sponsoring cooperation and discussion between gifted children's advocacy groups and educational personnel, sponsorship of Explorers' Clubs (children's groups), assistance in identifying children, providing speakers for professional and lay groups, briefing newspapers and radio on programs for the gifted, and conducting an annual conference. One gets the impresssion half-way 'round the world of a highly active and effective group.

NEW BRUNSWICK ASSOCIATION FOR GIFTED

A newcomer to organizations for the gifted is the New Brunswick Association for Gifted Children and Adults in Canada which organized last autumn and published its first quarterly journal in November with Professor David Willings as President. It is sponsored by the University of New Brunswick and plans to establish a Saturday Club for gifted children, provide communication within the province on the gifted, conduct conferences on specific themes,

(continued on page 8)

"BARGAIN" FEE OFFERED FOR NEW BIENNIUM

Membership fees are being accepted now for the coming biennium and will cover the period from payment date to 30 June 1985. The fee remains at \$30 (US) until action can be taken by the Executive Committee and Delegate Assembly to adjust dues in keeping with rising costs. Act now and avoid anticipated increase!

Membership expresses a commitment to extension of opportunities for gifted and talented children and to increasing research on the phenomenon of giftedness. In material terms, it includes subscription to the newsletter, World Gifted, the journal, Gifted International. It opens pathways to communication with similarly committed persons world-wide and offers admission to special events at the biennial World Conference.

GIFTED NEWS WORLD-WIDE- (Cont. from p. 7) and present an annual conference (in 1983, on March 25-26; theme: *Is There Life after School?*) Contact: Dr. J. M. Tolliver, Secretary, 105 Canterbury Drive, Fredericton, N.B. E3B 4L7. Proceedings of the 1982 Conference, *The Gifted at University*, are now available. Papers on tertiary education of the gifted by Dr. Willings and Dr. Tolliver are included.

DIRECTORY FOR GRADUATE STUDENT NETWORK

Arlene Dover has been working assiduously to develop a directory of student members of the World Council. Since student members are not currently identified in our files, Students are asked to write to Arlene Dover, % B. Shore, Faculty of Education, McGill University, 3700 McTavish St., Montreal PQ H3A 1Y2.

APPLICATION FOR MEMBERSHIP

To: Milton J. Gold, Executive Secretary, World Council for Gifted and Talented Children, Box 218, Teachers College, New York, NY 10027

I enclose a check for 30 US dollars to cover my subscription to the World Council for the Biennium ending June 30, 1985. Fee includes issues of Gifted International (Journal of the Council) and World Gifted (newsletter). N.B. Fee is applicable only until June 1, 1983. Increase in dues is anticipated after that date.

Name (printed or typed): _____

Occupation and title: _____

Address: _____

Renewal; New Membership

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